

The first successful atomic bomb psychological war and global cell security

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Summary

In today's world, the number of global nuclear weapons far exceeds the amount needed to destroy the earth, yet it is difficult to significantly reduce and eliminate them. After the Russia-Ukraine war, Europe and the United States are worried about Russia's use of nuclear weapons. The Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, which is ten times more powerful than that of the Chernobyl, has been repeatedly attacked by armed forces and its facilities have been damaged. Calculations show that if a full-scale nuclear explosion occurs at this power plant after being attacked, the theoretical disaster area is about 512 million km², which will exceed the area of the earth and all human cells will be completely destroyed. Since the global public does not know that the atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki were psychological warfare, they do not believe that 100 explosions at the level of the first nuclear explosion in New Mexico is enough to plunge the earth into a nuclear winter. According to data inference, two atomic bombings should have paralyzed at least 20% of Japan. But the opposite was true. Obviously, just this scientific logic is enough to prove that the US military successfully conducted psychological warfare at that time. If global human cells want to escape nuclear destruction, first of all, the public should be fully aware that the atomic bombings in Japan were fictional psychological warfare.

Keywords: Atomic bombing, Hiroshima, psychological war, Zaporizhzhia nuclear power, nuclear security, nuclear destruction, cell security

Reasons why it is difficult to significantly reduce and completely eliminate nuclear weapons

During the Russia-Ukraine war, Russia's views on the use of nuclear weapons attracted global attention.^{1,2} According to simulations by British and American scientists, only 100 nuclear weapons are needed to disrupt global ecological stability.^{3,4} A large number of radioactive particles float into the air and suspend for a long time, triggering a nuclear winter, leading to large-scale deaths in the world and the destruction of the entire human civilization. However, many people mistakenly believe that the idea that 100 nuclear warheads can destroy the world is a fallacy. Because the atomic bomb explosion in Hiroshima returned to normal weather after 2 - 3 weeks,⁴ and a few years later, the city flourished again. Even the world's top professionals have made wrong judgements. Only when 250 of the 13,000 nuclear weapons in the world are dropped will a "limited" nuclear war occur, which is believed to cause only 120 million direct

deaths and global climate damage.^{2,5}

The authors believe that the nuclear weapons policies of countries around the world today are closely related to the fact that the secret of the successful psychological warfare of atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki has not been made public to this day.^{6,7} The public failed to realize the enormous damage caused by nuclear explosions.

The psychological warfare carried out by the U.S. military in dropping atomic bombs in Japan inevitably required creating numerous false appearances, and required Japan to be deceived or cooperate, while utilizing the media to make the public largely believe in the predetermined results. However, the occurrence of fake atomic bomb explosions in the public domain inevitably has unavoidable logical errors and scientific paradoxes. Only one or two key pieces of evidence are needed to accurately determine whether it was psychological warfare.

The atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki are other evidences of psychological warfare

First, scientists from the U.S., China, and Australia used finite element analysis with giant computers to analyze footage of atomic bomb explosions in New Mexico,⁸ Hiroshima, and Nagasaki. Their surprising result was that the three sets of images were the same atomic bomb, meaning the footage was shot from different angles of the same explosion, likely the one in New Mexico. From logical perspective, or according to the evaluation standards of the U.S. FDA for process authenticity, this alone can also determine that the U.S. fabricated the atomic bombing of Hiroshima.

Second, in the photos taken at the center of the Hiroshima atomic bomb explosion, the area around the buildings was flattened, with residual buildings remaining on the flat ground, which contradicts the principles of an atomic bomb explosion.³ Many of the remaining walls on the flat ground were shattered on both sides, yet the walls remained standing, which is absolutely contradictory to any explosion theory. From logical perspectives, this alone suggests that the United States made false claims about the Hiroshima atomic bomb. The possibility is that some explosives were placed in a scattered manner, but there were no explosives near the contact point between the house wall and the ground. As a result, after the explosion, there were walls that did not collapse. This alone is equally sufficient to prove that the U.S. has implemented nuclear psychological warfare.

Third, within 50 years of the atomic bomb explosion, traces of most of the 200 radioactive substances are sure to be found in the soil around the explosion center. However, American and German scientists collected soil samples from Hiroshima and Nagasaki after the explosions and found that these soils were almost indistinguishable from normal soil, with no abnormal radiation levels.⁸ This alone is enough to confirm that the U.S. has implemented psychological warfare.

Fourth, between 1948 and 1954, scientists monitored almost all pregnancies in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and found no "statistically significant" increase in birth defects. The father of the atomic bomb, J. Robert Oppenheimer publicly stated after the dropping of the atomic bomb on Hiroshima,⁹ "there is every reason to believe that there was no appreciable radioactivity on the ground in Hiroshima." Based on this alone, it

can be judged that the atomic bomb explosions were indeed psychological warfare.

Fifth, analysis of military behavioral economy to paralyze a country with nuclear war.

Considering the recommendation of **the Chief Medical Officer of the Manhattan Project** that no one should be within 150 miles of the site of an atomic bomb explosion,^{10,11} Based on the power of the first nuclear weapon explosion, the author calculated the minimum number of atomic bombs required for mutual paralysis between different countries. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 The approximate minimum number of nuclear bombs needed to paralyze a country or Continent or the Earth

Country or Continent	Approximate area (Km ²) ¹²	Calculated value [★]	Minimum integer	Actual quantity ¹³
Russia	17.0982 million	93.44 / 133.49	94 / 134	4,489
USA	9.834 million	53.74 / 76.78	54 / 77	3,708
China	96,340,570	52.65 / 75.22	53 / 76	410
France	Land-area: 672834, mainland-area: 553,965	3.03-3.68 / 4.32-5.25	4 / 5-6	290
UK	244,100	1.33 / 1.91	2 / 2	225
India	2.98 million	16.29 / 23.27	17 / 24	164
Pakistan	880,254	4.81 / 6.87	5 / 7	170
North Korea	122,762	0.67 / 0.96	1 / 1	30
Israel	Actual-controlled-area: 25,740	0.14 / 0.20	1 / 1	90
Japan [▲]	377,972	(2.07 / 2.95), 4.77/6.82	(3 / 3), 5/7	
Ukraine	603,700	3.30 / 4.71	4 / 5	
Europe	10.16 million	55.53 / 79.32	56 / 80	
North America	24.228 million	132.41 / 189.15	133 / 190	
South America	17.84 million	97.50 / 139.28	98 / 140	
Africa	30.22 million	165.15 / 235.94	166 / 236	
Asia	44.579 million	243.63 / 348.04	244 / 349	
the Earth	510,067,866	2,787.56/3,982.23	2,788/3,983	

★ The data on the left is the minimum number of atomic bombs needed to paralyze an area calculated based on the power of the first atomic bombing in New Mexico (Skinny). The data on the right is based on the results after the explosion of the "Little Boy".

▲ According to the total north-south length of Japan's territory (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, and Kyushu mainland islands, excluding small islands), being approximately less than 2,300 km, it is calculated that about 5 Skinny-class atomic bombs or 7 Little

Boy-class atomic bombs are needed to destroy Japan.

Table 1 shows that the minimum number of nuclear bombs needed to paralyze Japan after a nuclear attack is about 5 or 7. When two atomic bombs explode in Hiroshima and Nagasaki, respectively, at least 20% of the area and cities near the two cities, accounting for about 20% of Japan's territory, will be paralyzed. It is worth noting that on August 9, 1945, the United States dropped the "Fat Man" atomic bomb on Nagasaki. It weighed about 4.9 tons and had a TNT equivalent of 22,000 tons, which was more powerful than Hiroshima's "Little Boy" and the world's first atomic bomb. However, three weeks later, there was no sense of nuclear pollution in Hiroshima and Nagasaki.⁴ The surrounding multiple cities and rural areas did not experience a situation where people could not survive due to the nuclear radiation caused by the atomic bomb explosions in these two cities. According to FDA standards for authenticating the process, it is clear that the atomic bombing of Japan was clearly a successful psychological warfare operation. After 80 years, the disclosure of this table's data makes any secrecy seem futile. Instead, it benefits Japan, a World War II war criminal country, which wants to portray itself as a victim of a nuclear attack. It is also not conducive to nuclear disarmament, to reducing military expenditures, to preventing nuclear power plant explosions, and to normalizing the economies of various countries.

The long-term concealment of Japan's atomic bomb psychological war has damaged the military and national defense economies of many countries.

Research by the Brookings Institution in Washington shows that from World War II to 2007, the U.S. government spent a total of \$7.2 trillion on nuclear weapons.¹⁴ Since the atomic bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, the United States has produced about 70,000 nuclear weapons.¹⁴ When the Cold War officially ended in 1991, the United States had 23,000 nuclear warheads.¹⁴ As for the former Soviet Union, by 1988, it had produced a total of about 43,000 nuclear weapons.¹⁵

Did both the U.S. and the former Soviet Union need so many nuclear bombs? According to the calculation results of this study, the success of concealing the psychological warfare of the atomic bombs in Hiroshima and Nagasaki led to a lack of real understanding of the power of nuclear weapons among even later U.S. leadership, and a lack of serious consideration of war or military or defense behavioral economics. The power of modern nuclear bombs is usually ten to several hundred times that of the first nuclear bomb. One can destroy Britain and France, and three hydrogen bombs can destroy the mainland of the United States. Excessive nuclear weapons are completely useless. The power of radioactive nuclear bombs lies in being stored in arsenals and nuclear bases, rather than being launched. Therefore, the number of nuclear bombs owned by any nuclear-weapon State should not exceed 1 - 5 at most. If humanity does not want to be destroyed, all nuclear weapons on Earth should be abolished. Apparently, not disclosing the truth of nuclear psychological warfare in Hiroshima has led to wrong nuclear weapons policies, crazy production, hindrance of peace, and huge economic losses for both countries and the world.

Over the past 70 years, the United States has continuously invested \$7.2 trillion in the military field of nuclear weapons. It seems to have driven regional economic growth or economic growth for a period of time, but in fact, it has suffered huge losses. This is investment behavior that does not conform to economic ethics and management ethics. From 1965-2018, the S&P 500 returned a total of 15,019%. So, one dollar invested in 1965 would be worth \$15,019 at the end of 2018.¹⁶ If the United States aims at long-term investment and entrusts a good investment team to invest. For example, Buffett's team invests \$1 trillion of funds used for nuclear weapons in stocks in the S&P index. As the index increases, investment income will increase to \$15,019 trillion. Even if half of the above assets are obtained, the income is extremely considerable. How could the United States have the current national debt crisis? How could the U.S. possibly force other countries to buy U.S. bonds to ease its own financial crisis? The United States is still the richest country in the world today. If the United States uses the obtained investment income for various expenditures in the United States, it is a very easy investment behavior to add 500,000 kilometers of high-speed rail in the United States. Basic medical care for Americans can be completely free. Housing for American families can be completely tax-free. All learning expenses for primary and secondary school students and college students in public universities in the United States can be waived completely. Obviously, in the long-term process of national governance, the economic operation and management of the United States have shown conditions of hypertension and stroke diseases. The economic operation of the United States shows government behavior economy and party behavior economy in large quantities every year. Looking back at history from a macro perspective, the military economy in the field of nuclear weapons in the United States largely shows the characteristics of a planned economy, but in the absence of ethics, it has plunged the U.S. into treasury bond crisis.

Table 2 Analysis of Investment Income Growth in the US Securities Market

Capital	Years	Annual compound investment return rate	Total principal and earnings (trillion)
\$7.2 trillion	54	From 1965-2018, the S&P 500 returned a total of 15,019%. So, a single dollar invested in 1965 would be worth over \$15,000 at the end of 2018.	108,136.8
\$1 trillion	54		15,019
\$100 billion	54		1,501.9
\$10 billion	54		150.19
\$10 billion	54	From 1965-2018, Berkshire Hathaway returned 2,472,627% . A single dollar invested in Berkshire Hathaway in 1965 would be worth over \$2.4 million by the end of 2018.	2,472.627
\$1 billion	54		247.2627

In poorly managed countries, there have been many incidents of ammunition depot explosions. If the U.S. or Russia falls into an economic crisis and mishandles aging

nuclear weapons, it could lead to serious problems. A nuclear base typically holds at least 5-20 strategic nuclear weapons. Once one explodes, a chain reaction of nuclear weapons inside the base is inevitable, possibly leading to Europe, the U.S. or North America become uninhabited restricted areas.

Fictional atomic bombings in Japan encouraged Japan's psychology of nuclear retaliation against the U.S.

According to media reports, at a gathering of Japanese Liberal Democratic Party politicians, the son of former Prime Minister Koizumi shouted, "Destroy the U.S. and give it 500 hydrogen bombs."¹⁷ Later, other senior members of the Liberal Democratic Party also shouted this sentence. There are currently 47 tons of nuclear material in Japan,¹⁸ but it has consistently refused to sign the nuclear deal, which has shocked the world. There is no doubt that Japan is sending a signal to the world that Japan will not give up nuclear weapons research and development. Last century, Japan massacred at least 50 million people in China and plundered huge amounts of wealth.⁶ Once Japan possesses nuclear weapons, it poses a great threat to the U.S. and global peace.

What is the power of the Sarmat nuclear bomb explosion?

The explosion of a Russian Sarmat nuclear bomb is equivalent to the power of 1,600 Little Boys.^{19,20} After the explosion of the Sarmat nuclear bomb, it will cover 204.9 million square kilometers. The total area of Europe, Africa and Asia is 10.16, 30.22 and 44.579 million square kilometres, respectively. If a Sarmat nuclear bomb explodes at a suitable location and altitude in Europe and exerts 70% of its power, not only Europe, but also Africa and Asia will be completely destroyed, and the Earth will enter a nuclear winter.

The real deterrent range after nuclear explosions at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant

Xinhua News Agency reported that on the evening of August 11, 2024,²¹ the Ukrainian army carried out two drone attacks on one of the two main cooling towers of the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, causing a fire in the main cooling tower, and both accused each other of causing the accident. Its internal structure was severely damaged. Experts will assess whether the main cooling tower is at risk of collapse when conditions permit.

Since the outbreak of the war between Russia and Ukraine, the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant has been bombed many times, and neither side is willing to take responsibility for this. This is very dangerous for Europe and the world. Obviously, the frequent attacks on the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant indicate that the global public and attackers were influenced by the psychological warfare of the atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and failed to truly understand the extent of the disaster caused by the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant explosion.

The amount of radioactive material released by the Chernobyl nuclear accident was approximately 400 times that of the atomic bombing in Hiroshima.^{22,23} Had it not been for the sacrifice of 600,000 Soviet citizens who voluntarily carried out rescue

operations to prevent a nuclear explosion, nuclear pollution would have covered 51.2 million square kilometers, which exceeded the total area of Europe and Africa. The entire Europe, Russia will be destroyed, and part of Asia and half of Africa would have been severely polluted. These former Soviet heroes, knowing that a nuclear explosion could occur at any time, still threw themselves into transporting various materials to reduce the threat of the nuclear accident. They were not afraid, although they knew that their lives would be sacrificed after exposure to nuclear radiation. People can live healthily on the planet today is inseparable from their selfless sacrifice and dedication to their lives.

Ukraine's Foreign Minister said that if a nuclear explosion occurred at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, the destructiveness would be equivalent to 10 Chernobyls,²⁴ which means that the theoretical area of the disaster caused without rescue after the accident is about **512.34** million square kilometers, which exceeds the area of the Earth. The social systems of both Russia and Ukraine are no longer socialist systems controlled by the Communist Party with a spirit of sacrifice. It is difficult for both Russia and Ukraine to have organized large numbers of people willing to sacrifice themselves to stop the repeated explosions and release of nuclear radiation at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant. Just like the Fukushima, almost no Japanese were willing to sacrifice themselves to control the nuclear power plant that had an accident. This means that not only the whole of Ukraine is destroyed, but also the entire Russia, Europe, America, Africa, Oceania and the Earth is ruined. The whole world is also severely polluted, and almost all humans and all humans' cells on Earth will die.

However, currently, people from Earth have been deceived by the false atomic bombings in Hiroshima and Nagasaki and cannot truly understand that once the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, whose power is equivalent to 4,000 Little Boy-level atomic bombings, even if 50-60% of the destruction is released, which areas of the world will be destroyed? What will be the number of victims?

Therefore, in order to prevent a nuclear explosion at the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant etc. after being attacked in the Russia-Ukraine war and the resulting destruction of all humans' cells, and to prevent a nuclear weapons war triggered by the Russia-Ukraine war and the consequent extinction of humanity. The world must be fully aware of the fact that the dropping of atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki was a successful psychological warfare operation, in order to achieve nuclear disarmament. The international community, international peace organizations, and personnel with in-depth research on nuclear weapons should make independent judgements as soon as possible based on scientific logic regarding whether the atomic bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki were part of nuclear psychological warfare. The United Nations and world peace organizations should convene one or more conferences on nuclear disarmament and peace. If nuclear weapons cannot be completely destroyed at once, it is recommended to reduce nuclear weapons and the disarmament of nuclear forces in two steps. Every country that already possesses nuclear weapons should at least reduce the number of its nuclear weapons to 1 to 5 and completely destroy them all within the next 3 to 10 years, in order to establish amicable relations among countries.

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Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests. No financial support

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